

Impact Objectives

- Assemble organic molecules into biodegradable nanoparticles featuring much higher brightness than single dye molecules
- Implement into nanoparticles a capacity to light-up or change the colour in response to single biomolecules, such as proteins and nucleic acids
- Use nanoparticle technology to its full capacity by using it as an analytical tool in both cancer cell research and medical diagnostics

A brighter future

*The potential of nanoparticles and bioimaging from the perspective of biological research and medical applications is huge, but there are some challenges to overcome. Dr Andrey Klymchenko expands on the work of the **BrightSens** project which is investigating the use of fluorescent biodegradable nanoparticles in bioimaging*

What were the key drivers behind the BrightSens project?

Molecular probes based on fluorescent dyes are

powerful and flexible, but their brightness is not always sufficient, which further limits sensitivity of the molecule-based fluorescence detection assays. We would like to assemble molecules together into smart nanoparticles featuring much higher brightness than single dye molecules. The second challenge we face is related to the fluorescent particles themselves, because so far, nanoparticles are mainly used as simple labels, not as probes for biomolecules. There was also an urgent need for new tools for detection of proteins and nucleic acids. At the cellular level, the current methods frequently require fixation or even destruction of the cells, whereas we strive to detect biomolecules directly in living cells.

How will ultra-bright organic nanoparticles help sensing in live cells?

Detection of biomolecules, such as membrane receptors and messenger RNAs (mRNA) in living cells is not an easy task. In the case of mRNA, only hundreds of copies of the same molecule are present inside a eukaryotic cell. However, this is far below the detection limits of current imaging techniques. Therefore, to detect certain proteins and RNA, the cells should be fixed (killed) and even destroyed in order to perform further analysis. Methods based on fluorescent molecules are not

effective enough to detect quantitatively single molecules in living cells because of their limited brightness. In this respect, fluorescent nanoparticles are particularly promising because they can be up to 100 times brighter than fluorescent dyes. Their use in the intracellular detection of biomolecules should finally make single molecules visible directly inside live cells.

Can you explain how the dyes change their colour and intensity in response to environment polarity?

Solvatochromic dyes can change their colour in response to environment polarity. In highly polar water they can emit red colour, whereas in apolar oil they switch their colour to either green or blue. This is due to their capacity to interact with molecules in their surroundings. Thus, strong dipole-dipole interactions of these dyes with polar molecules of water decrease the energy of their excited state and result in the red emission. In apolar media these interactions are weak, thus explaining their emission in the high energy blue region. This colour change is very important for biosensing, because biomolecules present significantly lower environment polarity compared to water (Klymchenko, Acc. Chem. Res., 2017).

What is the collective ON/OFF switching phenomenon?

We discovered the collective on/off switching of dyes inside polymers in 2014 (Reisch et al, Nat. Commun, 2014). When we studied nanoparticles encapsulating

100-500 dyes per particle, we found they undergo nearly complete on/off switching (blinking). This means 100-500 dyes can be switched on and off simultaneously, which does not sound obvious at all. This collective switching is related to a strong communication of dyes, so that more than 100 dyes in a particle behave like a single molecule. We successfully used this collective behaviour to switch on/off particle fluorescence by applying red or blue light, respectively. In our project, we plan to use this collective behaviour as a mechanism for the detection of biomolecules.

Is in vivo imaging using nanoparticles likely to become the accepted means of cell investigation?

When applied to small animals, nanoparticles can drastically increase the circulation time of the imaging agent in blood, and localise much more specifically in the target tumour tissues in comparison to imaging agents based on molecules. Moreover, nanoparticles, unlike small molecules, can carry multiple functions: they can bear different imaging agents for multi-modal imaging (for example fluorescence and MRI) or they can bear both imaging and therapeutic agents for theranostics. However, the use of nanoparticles creates some concerns related to the long-term toxicity in vivo, which is difficult to evaluate. Therefore, when designing nanoparticles for in vivo imaging applications, one should think about biodegradable nanoparticles.

Breaking down barriers

The BrightSens project led by Dr Andrey Klymchenko is hoping to revolutionise non-invasive medical examination. Here he explains how his team are working to improve the effectiveness of bioimaging and the use of nanoparticles as probes for biomarkers of diseases such as cancer

There is growing interest in how nanoparticles may offer new opportunities for cell analysis in biomedicine. These particles are typically small enough to be able to enter living systems, such as individual cells and potential areas of interest. Fluorescent particles appear as promising alternatives to existing fluorescent molecular probes, because they can be much brighter than organic dyes. However, while bright nanoparticles already exist, they are usually unable to respond to single molecular stimuli and tend not to be biodegradable.

Bioimaging has grown at a phenomenal rate. The technology covers a huge range of now well-established methods, such as X-ray and ultrasound imaging, MRI, 3D and 4D body imaging by CT scans. On the other hand, optical imaging, which is a common technique in the research laboratory, is still an emerging tool in medicine. The use of optical bioimaging for research and clinical diagnostics is highly attractive because it is much less expensive and simpler than other techniques. Moreover, fluorescence bioimaging has molecular specificity, which

means it enables direct detection of a desired biomolecule inside living cells or animals.

One of the most exciting processes is the use of fluorescent nanoparticles to accurately map cellular activity, however current systems fail due to low luminosity levels. The BrightSens project, overseen by Dr Andrey Klymchenko, aims to redress this and develop new technology surrounding ultra-bright fluorescent organic nanoparticles (FONs). These are capable of converting a single biomolecular stimuli into a collective response of many dyes in a particle that can be easily viewed.

Currently, fluorescence bioimaging is carried out using organic dyes and inorganic quantum dots – semiconductor particles between five and 50 nm across – which, while they are several orders brighter than the dyes, are generally not broken down in the body once inserted. However, this imbalance is being redressed by the use of ultra-bright nanoparticles derived from polymer drug-delivery vehicles, which are able to travel to intra-cellular sites

due to being organic, and are therefore biodegradable and of low toxicity.

LOW FLUORESCENCE PROBLEMS

There are many advanced medical applications for such nanoparticle biosensors, including their use as analytical tools in cell research; in vivo sensors for real-time detection; and accurate visualisation of analytes – such as glucose concentration – and physical structures within the body. While fluorescent molecules capable of mapping these are already available, their limited brightness does not allow the imaging of individual biomolecules in living cells.

At the beginning of the BrightSens project, the size and form of the particles were not well-controlled, but it was understood that for intracellular applications, the particles should be as small as possible, perhaps as small as 5-20 nanometres (with one nanometre being 1x10⁻⁹ metres). The team has found that with advanced molecular design, polymerised micellar particles of around seven nm across can be reliably

manufactured, making them comparable in size to that of a single protein (Shulov et al, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2016). Plainly, they are the smallest fluorescent organic particles of such high brightness developed until now, which opens up potentially new areas of biomedical applications.

Higher levels of luminosity are achieved by confining large amounts of dye in a correspondingly small space, effectively increasing the absorption coefficient.

Unfortunately however, side effects such as aggregation caused quenching have limited the effectiveness of the dye-loaded polymer nanoparticles, thereby decreasing their fluorescence quantum yield and effectively limiting their brightness. This has been countered to a large extent by controlling dye organisation inside the particles, which have reduced this quenching effect, allowing increased fluorescence in the polymers and achieving a superior brightness.

The BrightSens team are currently implementing a biosensor function into these ultrabright nanoparticles. From that point, the development of highly sensitive probes for the detection of cancer markers will be key to biological research and medical applications. These new probes are expected to positively impact development of new tools for rapid diagnostics of cancer.

WORK PACKAGE APPROACH

The development of ultrabright fluorescent nanoparticle systems, capable of converting single molecular stimuli into an amplified turn-on or colour response, requires a significant effort on many different research fronts. Klymchenko sees this work as breaking down into three separate, but related streams. The first part involves the synthesis of FONs through either loading dyes into polymeric particles or assembly of protein-sized micellar FONs to enable precise control of dye organisation within the nanoparticles. Following this, nanoprobe will be designed based on Förster Resonance Energy Transfer mechanism to produce FONs that undergo complete turn-on or colour change in response to single molecular targets. Once these two steps have been completed, the FONs will be directed towards cellular applications, and tested in a series of cancer cell lines to check whether the fluorescent nanoparticles are able to ensure detection of important markers such as membrane receptors and intracellular mRNA.

Initial work has focused on fabrication of nanoparticles, while also reducing their size appropriately, implementing on/off

‘The capacity of nanoparticles to respond to external stimuli is key to ultra-sensitive detection systems. Unlike classical detection systems, where one fluorescent dye lights-up in response to the target biomolecule, in our design strategy, detection of one biomolecule could light up hundreds of dyes inside a nanoparticle’

switching capability and ensuring they were stable in cells and biological fluids, so they are able to target areas of interest while in an intact form. The team has already prepared particles of controlled sizes ranging from seven to 80 nm that are many-fold brighter than commercial quantum dots and stable in cells and even in living animals, taking the project forward significantly.

ECO-FRIENDLY SYSTEM

Since the fluorescent nanoparticles are essentially biodegradable, they can be considered to be eco-friendly too. Biodegradability will also help to smooth the way forward for FDA and international approval for medical use. These factors make them attractive for use in biological systems and safe to introduce into the environment.

The ultrabright fluorescent nanoparticle probes being developed by the BrightSens project will be compatible with low-powered equipment such as specially developed smartphones, allowing easy, low-cost detection of disease biomolecular markers available to medical professionals. The BrightSens project will allow the observation and tracking of diseases such as cancer from very early stages, and help identify the actual type of carcinoma detected.

Klymchenko sees these ultrabright fluorescent nanoparticle materials as a future major tool in initial examination and identification of disease-related anomalies at the molecular and cellular levels. Fluorescent nanoparticles are likely to become a powerful tool in medical diagnostics with potential impact on personalised medicine.

Project Insights

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PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR BIO

Andrey Klymchenko started his research with chemistry and photophysics of new fluorescent dyes, which was a subject of his PhD degree from Kiev National University, Ukraine in 2003. He worked in the University of Strasbourg, France, where he combined synthesis of new dyes with their bioimaging applications. In 2005, in order to extend his expertise towards supramolecular chemistry and nanotechnology, he moved to Catholic University of Leuven, Belgium. He obtained CNRS researcher position in 2006, received the CNRS Bronze Medal in 2010 and was promoted to Director of Research in 2014. In 2015, he obtained ERC consolidator grant BrightSens: “Ultrabright Turn-on Fluorescent Organic Nanoparticles for Amplified Molecular Sensing in Living Cells.”

